

Sustainability Blueprint Factory

Final Report

Nancy L. Maron
Valerie McNutt

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Authors

Nancy Maron, Lead, Sustainability Blueprint Factory; Principal, BlueSky to BluePrint, LLC

Valerie McNutt, Research Associate, BlueSky to BluePrint, LLC

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The SGX3 Blueprint Factories are intended to help SGX3 better understand the CI needs of entire research communities and national-scale cyberinfrastructure providers. Each Blueprint Factory brings together CI professionals, domain scientists, and major infrastructure operators to discuss current challenges and design solutions.

For more information on the SGX3 Blueprint Factories, please visit <https://sciencegateways.org/our-services/blueprint-factories>.

SGX3 Leadership Team

Sandra Gesing, SGX3 Director and PI

Maytal Dahan, Scientific Software Collaborative Lead and Co-PI

Linda Hayden, Workforce Development Lead and Co-PI

Claire Stirm, Consulting Lead and Co-PI

Janae Baker, Project Manager

Sean Cleveland, Blueprint Factory Lead

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Executive Summary

INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades the work of scholarship and education—research, writing, teaching, publishing—has slowly but inexorably continued to migrate online, morphing from paper to digital formats, from in-person to virtual workspaces. Few aspects of scholarship and teaching are now conducted without support in some digital form.

Science gateways are one manifestation of this ground shift, as the scientific research community identified the need to expand access to high-performance computing capacity for researchers and research institutions that might not otherwise have the expertise or financial resources needed to run complex computational analyses and simulations. The first generation of science gateways—user interfaces that permit researchers to execute computationally intensive work without needing to create the code to do so—offered a solution for expanding access to a wider scholarly community.

The rise of science gateways has mirrored similar efforts taking place in the humanities and social sciences, in library collections, and in the world of scholarly publishing: using technology to widely share the fruits of research and scholarship. While the specific content and tools may be quite different from the data sets and computational work of early science gateways, the underlying similarities were undeniable: large-scale websites, often hosting large amounts of scholar-created content, aggregated online in order to more easily provide wide access to a global audience of scholars and students, an act of heroic sharing of work that in decades past would have been greatly limited in its scope by the constraints of local geographies, travel budgets, and physical or monetary barriers to access.

As these science gateway creators and their cousins in the humanities and social sciences soon found, building a gateway is costly and complex, and nurturing it so it grows and continues to serve its target audience is even more so! The issue of “sustainability”—how to build gateways, digital humanities projects, library collections, and repositories that continue to be valuable and have reliable and recurring sources of support—has been a central challenge for each new community of practice as it has entered the digital realm.

GOALS OF THIS PROJECT

The Sustainability Blueprint Factory is a research project of the SGX3 Center of Excellence, an NSF-funded, multi-institutional service organization, whose mission is to “extend access, expand the community, and exemplify good practices for CI through science gateways.”¹ Since 2016, SGX3 and its precursor SGCI have worked with hundreds of gateways PIs and teams, observing first-hand the successes and challenges of creating and running a science gateway. The Sustainability Blueprint Factory is one of three Blueprint Factories currently underway. Its aim is to take stock of significant progress over the past 15 years, surface key challenges that still exist, and—perhaps most important—shine a light on promising approaches to addressing those persistent challenges.

Today the notion of science gateway has expanded beyond its original remit to provide access to HPC, and this report embraces that broader view. This report includes examples from the worlds of STEM, humanities, and social sciences. Some of the innovative digital projects highlighted here self-identify as “science gateways” and others have leaders who might not recognize the term. We describe challenges facing large-scale, research-focused, digital initiatives that have the intention of widely sharing cyberinfrastructure, tools, data, or content, in the service of facilitating knowledge creation and sharing. If there is one key message underlying this exploration, it is that the challenges facing these seemingly disparate digital initiatives are so similar as to beg the question: Might there be bigger, bolder, more unified approaches to creating ways to support this still-new landscape of digital scholarship?

The report is structured in five sections, each dedicated to a major challenge facing leaders and supporters of these gateways. Each section begins with a review of the persistent challenge and progress made, offers examples of these approaches in action, and closes with a list of recommendations for future actions.

METHOD

Findings shared in this report are the result of an in-depth literature review and interviews with 35 people with deep experience in building and supporting science gateways. Focus groups addressed specific topics, such as institutional support and culture change. Individual interviews permitted the research team to further explore specific approaches by speaking with the people involved in them. A session at the 2024 annual Gateways conference elicited feedback from PIs attending the meeting. The authors drew findings from that work, and a draft report was shared for feedback with several readers.

TOPICS COVERED IN THE REPORT

The five key areas addressed in the report and the “approaches” to sustainability within them are:

Too many gateways, trying to do it all

Approach: Borrow, don't build. The rise of platforms

Approach: Convergence & “coopetition”

Institutional support: shifting focus over time

Approach: Emergence of campus-support hubs

Defining and delivering a strong value proposition

Approach: Building by placing user needs first

Approach: Training and consulting

Approach: Standardizing impact metrics

Sustainable funding

Approach: Collaborative funding

Approach: Funder “sustainability” tracks

Leadership, staffing, governance

Approach: Professionalization and the rise of the RSE

Approach: Culture of support

Approach: Governance models: rise of consortia

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR NEXT STEPS

Each section of the report includes a list of future directions and questions for discussion. Among the suggestions the report identifies are:

- Initiating a national discussion about challenges to identify elements of gateway support that could be managed and paid for at a collective level.
- Developing a taxonomy of science gateways to define and quantify them, according to domain, function, and structure. This framework, which could also produce an inventory, could help identify more operational commonalities and needs among what otherwise can appear to be a sea of one-off projects.
- Building modular tools and affordable platform solutions, perhaps by discipline, to reduce the need for PIs to build customized platforms.
- Expanding education and training in crafting value propositions and focusing on user needs: for grant applicants, new grantees, and mature project leads.
- Expanding funding support at the early stages of a project for often overlooked areas of expertise: strategy, marketing, and governance.
- Assessing the extent to which collaborative funding models have succeeded. What criteria have been most successful in identifying which projects to support?

CONCLUSION

Ideally, those who read this report—funders, principal investigators, administrators at research institutions and libraries—will find these examples useful, and will choose to explore or implement some of them. While the challenges facing gateways are often similar to those facing digital collections, digital humanities projects, educational websites, and others, the solutions today are still often siloed, and addressed field by field, even project by project. The scale needed to truly address the long-term robustness of the scholarly environment will require greater coordination and shared vision—within disciplines, across institutions, and across funders.

Introduction

In 2023, SGX3's Center of Excellence² launched a series of Blueprint Factories, research studies seeking community input to address key challenges facing the scientific research community by bringing together CI professionals, domain scientists, and major infrastructure operators through focus groups, surveys, and interviews.³ The first three Blueprint Factories were intended to focus on Artificial Intelligence, Materials Science, and Sustainability. The Factories on AI and Materials Science, underway at this writing, will identify needs that could be translated into technical tools or features for Science Gateway platforms and virtual research environments.

The Sustainability Blueprint Factory addresses challenges to the long-term viability and ongoing success of science gateways, the “online interfaces that give researchers, educators, and students easy access to shared resources that are otherwise inaccessible or unaffordable for a large segment of the scientific community.”⁴ Its aim is to define persistent challenges, surface examples of promising approaches, and encourage further exploration and action to create a robust, valuable, and sustainable online environment for scholarship.

Early gateways offered researchers access to high-performance computing (HPC), permitting researchers to engage in computational scientific research without having to know how to code. They were seen as a means of expanding access to HPC to new groups of users, vastly reducing the time and effort needed to analyze data, run simulations, or otherwise manipulate and analyze large, complex datasets.

In the 2000s, the National Science Foundation (NSF) supported the creation of major science gateways, such as **nanoHUB** (2002, a nanotechnology researcher community, enabling simulations) and CIPRES (2009, for evolutionary biologists who analyze DNA data to infer phylogenetic relationships). Something

similar was taking place across the disciplinary tracks. The National Endowment for the Humanities funded the development of **SlaveVoyages**, offering the public access to decades of research gathered in the Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database. Funding from the Mellon Foundation supported the creation of Oxford's **Electronic Enlightenment**, offering access to the digitized correspondence between great writers and thinkers throughout the 18th century. Humanists and social scientists were finding new ways to use technology to advance and widely share their work.

Today, a community-serving website need not offer access to computing capacity to be considered a "gateway." Some offer access to HPC; others do not. Some are rich with data sets; others offer tools to use with data the user provides. Some are used by researchers, others by instructors for teaching purposes. And while some gateways in STEM-related fields are essentially content collections—of articles, of datasets—more and more, humanities and social sciences projects are relying on access to HPC.⁵

For the purposes of this study, we adopt a broad definition of "gateway" to include not just those research platforms that self-identify as "science gateways" but any large-scale, research-focused, digital initiative that has the intention of widely sharing cyberinfrastructure, tools, data, or content, in the service of facilitating knowledge creation and sharing. The reason for adopting such a wide net is that this study is concerned with the challenges of supporting and sustaining these community-focused digital initiatives. Whether STEM or humanities-focused, the challenges they face are remarkably similar.

Nearly two decades ago, major studies began addressing the challenges science gateways and other large-scale digital initiatives faced when attempting to move beyond their original grant funding, from "project" to service. The science community with NSF support, followed up on earlier studies and undertook large-scale surveys, exploring community needs for gateways.⁶ The UK-based funder JISC, and the NEH sought answers through detailed case studies of sustainability strategies for digital projects in a range of disciplines.⁷ Still others focused on the approaches universities were taking to offer support.⁸ The world of academic libraries, deeply involved in large-scale digitization work and creation of digitized special collections, identified sustainability as a challenge⁹ and also recognized the need to address the "website problem" that was emerging.¹⁰ Some of this "expansive digital publishing" continues to be a challenge, not fitting neatly into established methods for distribution, discovery, or long-term support.¹¹ Similar discussions were taking place concerning research software itself.^{12, 13}

The **Sustainability Blueprint Factory** takes those early reports as a starting point, and through interviews and focus groups with dozens of experts and practitioners in a range of fields, attempts to answer the questions:

- What has changed in the landscape since then?
- What challenges to sustainability persist?
- Where are areas of progress and promising directions for change emerging?
- What changes or actions by gateway leaders, by funders, and by institutional hosts would help to create highly valuable resources that are well-used and well-supported?

The SGX3 Center of Excellence is an NSF-funded multi-institutional service organization, developed by the team that led the Science Gateways Community Institute.¹⁴ Since the original SGCI began in 2016, the team has supported over 150 gateways in a range of ways, including technical development, user experience, community development and business strategy.¹⁵ By bringing together our experiences and the voices of experts across a wide range of fields, the aim of this report is to document the advances made and areas of progress, while also spotlighting areas still very much in need of work.

Ultimately, these findings and recommendations are intended to catalyze discussion and debate, leading to concrete actions that will improve the current ecosystem of creation and support. The goal is that researchers, teachers, students and even the public can have access to the high-quality tools, software, gateways, and other innovative digital resources that they need to continue to explore and improve our world.

Background

WHAT IS SUSTAINABILITY?

Sustainability, like “success,” can be difficult to define. For this study, we take as a starting point the notions of sustainability that pinpoint value to users as the underlying engine:

“ Sustainability is the ability to generate or gain access to the resources – financial or otherwise – needed to protect and increase the value of the content or service for those who use it.”¹⁶

A similar notion of sustainability has emerged in relation to academic software. Daniel S. Katz notes that sustainability is “the capacity of the software to endure. In other words, sustainability means that the software will continue to be available in the future, on new platforms, meeting new needs.”¹⁷ Both definitions carry with them the implication that something permits the software—or gateway—to be supported and improved over time. That “something” comes back to people—the value that users find in software, or a gateway is the central component, the special sauce in these definitions, and the key to determining if a science gateway or a piece of software will have a long life.

SUSTAINABILITY IS A CHALLENGE FOR ALL INNOVATIVE ONLINE RESOURCES

Sustainability emerged as a critical issue related to digital resources in the 2000s, as funders in education and academic research invested in rounds of innovative digital platforms, collections, and

infrastructure. Funders had noticed that while project teams might be able to execute the plans as outlined in the funded proposals, they struggled to keep building and maintaining the digital resources after launch; the teams returned to their funders in search of further rounds of financial support, without a clear path for independence.¹⁸

This pattern troubled both government and private funders, who preferred to support new and innovative areas of research, but also wished to see their investments thrive independently. It also troubled the project leaders themselves, many leading active careers as researchers and scholars. While they were passionate about these new digital creations, they were not planning to devote all their time to supporting them, and yet they often found themselves spending far more time than anticipated doing just that.

Funder investments in academic digital initiatives in the US, UK, Europe, and Australia fueled experiments and investments across all fields, from the humanities and social sciences to STEM fields; from library-based special collections to research cyberinfrastructure. Among the US-based, nonprofit funders engaged in these early investments were The Mellon Foundation (then, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation), via digital humanities and scholarly communications infrastructure grants; the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation via projects like the Sloan Digital Sky Survey; the Institute of Museum and Library Services National Leadership Grants program; and the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation's investment in the open course materials movement. The US government invested in cyberinfrastructure, gateways, and teaching materials in a range of scientific fields via the NIH, DOE, NOAA, NSF, and others, including the NSF's National Science Digital Library. In the UK, examples include JISC's support of digitization projects and research platforms as well as the New Opportunities Fund's digitization program investing mainly in library digitization projects, just to name a few.¹⁹

The variety and range of types of projects has been impressive as well, from large-scale projects that have supported science researchers for decades, like Protein Data Bank, to those addressing teaching and learning needs, such as ChemCompute, created by a professor for teaching undergraduate chemistry.

And yet, despite the broad range of scholarly questions these projects address, the forms these projects can take, and the sheer number of academic fields involved, these projects share many characteristics.

These innovative, community-facing digital initiatives share:

- A focus on supporting knowledge creation and sharing
- A mission to facilitate sharing of high-quality content, data, tools, and software with researchers and students (and sometimes the general public)
- Technical infrastructure, tools, and interfaces that, once built, require ongoing support, maintenance, and upgrades
- Origins in grant (startup) funding, with an unclear path from startup to ongoing service
- An expectation of participation and interaction with a community

Gateways of all types trying to grow and thrive often struggle to:

- Develop reliable revenue streams, whether due to a reluctance or inability to engage in revenue-generation, still sometimes seen as at odds with a mission-based project
- Transition from experiment to reliable service and then navigate the change needed when a small group of academic researchers must become a customer-facing, customer-focused operation
- Adjust to prioritizing the needs of the community over one's own preferences
- Secure the expertise needed that may not be native to the core research team, such as project management, sales, marketing, and programming
- Fully understand user/stakeholder needs and act on that knowledge

Beyond those challenges, project leaders often operate in a world that does not fully recognize the value of their work or offer adequate paths for professional advancement. Guidance from a project's key stakeholders concerning what "success" looks like can be inconsistent. In particular, project leaders often note their frustration when attempting to raise funds to support a growing project, while managing funder guidelines and institutional barriers (and bureaucracy) that can make this incredibly difficult.

As we will describe later in this report, many funders have taken steps to address these challenges by creating funding tracks to give PIs time to build sustainability strategies, to coach PIs in needed skills, and to encourage teams to collaborate for scale. Project leaders themselves have taken steps, learning to write data management plans, drafting sustainability plans, and taking courses to improve their own skills at thinking about how to support and grow their gateways. Despite some progress, the fundamental challenges of building and maintaining a sustainable, viable digital project remain.

SUSTAINABILITY'S PERSISTENT CHALLENGES

The SGX3 team and its consultants have worked with hundreds of principal investigators, developers, and domain specialists engaged in creating and maintaining gateways of all sizes and forms who continue to struggle with finding ways to grow their audience and establish regular means of support. The funders who help create and develop these gateways are aware of the challenges of keeping a project viable, growing, and of value to its users. As a funder of digital projects noted, "I'm not sure the needle has moved very much [in the last several years].... Despite changes at [the funding body] ... sustainability challenges are still prevalent." Another noted, "not much has changed" over the last decade.

Scholars engaged in digital humanities work are seeing the same challenges in their fields. The recently published *Report of the Commission on Fostering and Sustaining ...Digital Scholarship* found that "a core challenge in digital humanities work remains unsolved: Much digital work lacks provision for enduring access and is at risk of loss. Building on more than two decades of digital experience, the scholarly communication community now needs to organize an integrated, coordinated effort to address gaps in publication and stewardship, and to articulate and implement expectations that are widely shared."²⁰

THE MOVE TO OPEN: A KEY STEP, NOT A COMPLETE SOLUTION

Perhaps one of the most revolutionary advances over the last two decades has been the move to "open": open access content, open source code, and open licensing. A generation ago, as the internet made it possible to rapidly share content digitally—without the cost of physical printing, copying, or mailing—the notion that publishers, who made a living from selling access, would also adopt models to make content freely accessible to users was at best a dream. Today, we see publishers of all types at least experimenting with open access models. Federal mandates from the Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) in 2022 required federal funders to make "publications and their supporting data resulting from federally funded research publicly accessible without an embargo on their free and public release."²¹

Thanks to advocacy, government policy and funder mandates have made scholarly content and tools openly and freely available to scholars and students. There are many wonderful reasons to rejoice about this massive shift: research is now often available sooner to more people. Scholarship and even teaching materials are often freely available. Open licenses, such as Creative Commons and the GNU General Public License make it easier to share works and software. Open source code presents the potential to have greater degree of sharing and collaborative building than ever before. And yet, even gateways that embrace open principles can continue to struggle with the challenges of identifying recurring sources of financial and non-financial support. Rather than a solution to sustainability, “open” is perhaps better thought of as a useful tool or even a starting point, around which a sustainability strategy must then be constructed.

Methodology

The **Sustainability Blueprint Factory** was designed to examine changes in the landscape over the last decade and to surface successful or promising approaches to sustainability that might merit further investigation or investment.

Over the course of eighteen months, the authors met with 35 individuals in interviews and focus groups. Participants were selected to represent a variety of roles and types of experience with the challenges of supporting and sustaining science gateways. Roles represented included principal investigators, funders, and campus leaders from a range of fields from STEM to digital humanities, and settings including academic departments, libraries, supercomputer centers, and funded projects, to gather a range of perspectives on the challenges, innovations and future trends in sustaining digital projects across the spectrum of knowledge. Interviews typically lasted 45-60 minutes.

STAGE 1: EXPLORATORY INTERVIEWS TO FRAME TOPICS

The first stage included a literature review, creation of an interview guide, and choice of some key areas of innovation. Interviews were conducted with members of the SGX3 leadership team, and with a handful of experts in the field. The interview structure followed a standard series of questions, covering three main areas:

- What do you see as the persistent challenges of sustainability today?
- What progress have you noticed in the last decade or so?
- What changes do you see that appear most promising? What would you like to see?

From those foundational interviews, we developed a list of topics as a starting point to explore further.²² Those topics included:

1. Campus-based approaches, in particular, support for open source software (OSS) Encouraging the use of open source software to maximize transparency, encourage community engagement, and open up the potential for community support.
2. Major cross-institutional efforts to identify and build for community needs. Partnerships, consortia, joint funding proposals, and other large-scale efforts to collaboratively address challenges.
3. New approaches and processes. New approaches to team dynamics, recognition, and leadership to aid sustainability.

STAGE 2: FOCUS GROUPS AND PI WORKSHOP

To better understand these three areas, we conducted two virtual focus groups in June and July 2024 focused on administrators in higher education institutions. Participants were based at public and private R1 and R2 universities working in areas such as Open Source Program Offices (OSPOs), libraries, digital humanities centers and tech transfer offices. The focus groups were 60–90 minutes long and included three to four participants each. A full list of participants is included in Appendix A.

In addition, we gathered perspectives from project PIs via a workshop at Science Gateways 2024, the annual conference held in September 2024 in Bozeman, Montana. Thirty conference attendees participated in a BrainTrust, a facilitated exercise designed to help groups ideate and prioritize findings. Participants self-selected into groups, choosing one of five topic areas:

- Increasing collaboration
- Growing an audience, scaling to size
- Funding and other types of sustaining support
- Staying relevant in a rapidly evolving space
- Increasing impact

For each topic area, a facilitator read a problem statement, and participants wrote down their thoughts and met in groups of two or three to consolidate their thinking and ideas. The ideas were shared and organized into three categories: Highest impact, important but costly, and wild and crazy.

STAGE 3: INTERVIEWS: FUNDERS AND DOMAIN EXPERTS

To understand in more detail some of the ideas raised in earlier phases, we undertook hour-long interviews with funders and with leaders of key projects about which we felt we needed to learn more. Funders included seven government organizations and private foundations in the U.S including the National Institutes of Health (NIH), The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, The Mellon Foundation, the National Science Foundation (NSF) and National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH). In addition, we interviewed experts working on some of the initiatives our work to date had highlighted to learn more about the specific approaches they are undertaking.

STAGE 4: REPORT AND COMMUNITY CONSULTATION

In late 2024, the report was shared with several readers with expertise in the field of gateways, software, and sustainability for feedback. Revisions and a discussion took place prior to publication. Further public discussions are planned post-publication.

Findings: Challenges and promising approaches

This section presents a distillation of findings culled from the interviews and focus groups conducted throughout the study. The original list of three themes was expanded to include additional topics raised by participants. The promising “approaches” offered here are examples intended to stimulate future discussion by sharing good practices, creative thinking, and emerging solutions. Each section offers an overview of the challenge observed, examples of progress or promising approaches, and suggestions for further action or exploration.

Challenge: Too many gateways, trying to do it all

Many science gateways begin as the brainchild of a researcher or team of researchers who propose a gateway concept which is then funded through grants, often from a large federal agency. While proposals optimistically describe the “community need” for a new gateway, experience has shown that many gateways fall short of becoming robust community resources and struggle to attract users and reliable sources of ongoing support.

Participants in this study suggested that an unintended consequence of academic independence and innovation is to produce an environment with too many similar projects, and projects built with too much customization.

Academic researchers are trained to identify research questions and methods that are unique or extend the value of work already done. Intellectual independence, while a critical mindset for a successful scholarly career, does not translate well when adopted by builders of science gateways. “Scholars are used to doing research on their own,” said Annelie Rugg, formerly Director and Humanities CIO at UCLA’s Humanities Technology, who is familiar with the work of faculty PIs. “[They] start from scratch each time, because it gives them full control. This model is not sustainable... [there is a need for] someone to tell them what is unique, and what is not.”

This tendency does not just apply to researchers-turned-gateway-builders. Professional research software engineers are often just as eager to build custom solutions. As the director of an advanced computing center whose teams support PIs from all disciplines noted, she sees “the challenge of reinventing the wheel... We have a framework, but there [are] still lots of side solutions.”

Funders have long recognized the tension of wanting to encourage the independence and creativity of the PIs they fund while—wherever possible—trying to convince grantees to fully make use of existing technical solutions before building their own. NIH Program Director Ishwar Chandramouliswaran noted that the system of funding itself, where “bigger is better” in terms of grant funding, can create “lots of disincentives” to proposing more efficient solutions to building a gateway using existing components. He also noted that some PIs have persistent misconceptions about what truly makes a science gateway valuable to its audience, resulting in too much original coding taking place, when “good enough” solutions already exist. While indeed there may be novel research questions that require original coding and new tools, as Michael Zentner, former director of the Science Gateways Community Institute noted, “discovering when to reinvent is a needed art.”

Over-engineering is a related issue which can have longer-range consequences as well, beyond the fragility and expense of the project itself. Megan Forbes, Program Manager of the Open Source Programs Office at Johns Hopkins University, sees in the social sciences, “people using bits and pieces of software they don’t even necessarily understand,” leading to additional challenges in reproducibility of the research itself.

Interoperability. PIs who support the idea of collaboration do not necessarily find it particularly easy to do in practice. And not all project leaders prioritize collaboration. A study conducted of the online publishing landscape inventoried over 50 open source projects, from large-scale platforms to highly specialized tools and found that, “[t]he goals of collaboration, interoperability, and integration are very secondary to the specific, internal goals of each project.”²³

Doing it all. Assuming that the gateway has indeed pinpointed a unique space in the gateway ecosystem and is filling a well-defined need, there are still real challenges in designing, launching and maintaining complex gateways. Even those who make good use of existing systems and software are faced with a set of ongoing activities that are necessary, but require different skills and more staff. This may be evidence of a broader, systemic challenge: take, for example, the world of traditional scholarly publishing, where the author/scholar was responsible for the research and writing of the book or article, at which point it was handed off to the expert staff of a professional publishing house to handle many other stages of work: editorial, production, design, promotion, marketing, distribution, and sales.

Today, for a scholar choosing to create a science gateway or digital humanities project **there is no handoff**. The PI awarded a grant to build the Great New Digital Resource is—implicitly—expected to take on or account for all stages of work, from concept to dissemination. The vertical stack of roles, each serving a distinct purpose in creating and getting a new intellectual work to “market”—to the users who need it—has largely collapsed in today’s science gateways/digital humanities world. The scholarly creator, once called upon just to deliver the results of scholarship to an expert team of publishing professionals with a range of skills to get that work out to the public, is often obliged to take responsibility for all the stages of work, from concept to build, to marketing and promotion, to finance.

Perhaps we are still in a transitional phase, as the shape of the digital scholarly ecosystem is still coming into focus. Digital builders are creating methods and paths—the roads and bridges—that will support future generations. But for now, gateway creators are still often developing projects that are new, bespoke, and carry the burden of far too many roles.

Approach: Borrow, don't build. The rise of platforms

If a surfeit of unsteady gateways with researcher-leaders trying to “do it all” with little support is the problem, what sort of solution might help? Robust, reliable platforms that offer off-the-shelf solutions for creating gateways could free scientists from the need to spend so much effort building and maintaining the infrastructure for the gateways they create. While there will always be the need for some degree of customization, how much shared infrastructure could be provided, and to what extent would this result in effort and cost-savings for gateway leaders?

Over the last decade, platforms and portals have emerged to host and share data and tools at scale. This is a strategy not limited to gateways or STEM fields, but also seen in scholarly publishing and academic library collections. Those responsible for technology solutions at research libraries have long noted the need to efficiently manage multiple digital collections.²⁴ Bohyun Kim, Associate University Librarian for IT at the University of Michigan has described the “struggle to support more than 80 IT products and to preserve content housed in many of those as much as possible [in light of] ... the limited resources and staff time and the limitation of infrastructure.” With “five large repositories ... running on four different platforms ... there is also the high level of legacy product”²⁵ to manage. Rob Cartolano, Associate Vice President for Digital Programs and Technology Services at Columbia University, notes that these challenges have led to a shift in building “more standardized and centrally run services whether they run at Columbia or [are] hosted by vendors... so that not everything has to be built in a bespoke, one-off way.”

One approach to creating—and having to support—multiple gateways, is to create robust platforms that make it possible for researchers to stand up their own sites using a common set of tools. While individual gateways on the platform may be customized, the underlying structure is built and managed by a single, stable organization.

An example of this is HUBzero, the open source software platform originally built to support the NSF-funded nanoHUB project²⁶ and embedded at Sustainable Scientific Software Division (S3D) at SDSC, has been in operation for twenty years and hosts over 20 gateways. Their model makes it possible for a project (often funded by NSF, NIH, or others) to build the cost of the platform into their grant budget and forgo the time and expense of building it themselves.

Some gateways (including some which are themselves hosted on HUBzero) have extended this model a step further:

- **BIOQuest's Quantitative Undergraduate Biology Education and Synthesis (QUBES)** is built on HUBzero, but itself provides a means for smaller projects to share and find learning materials. In this case, the QUBES model has the double benefit of offering low-cost solutions to smaller builders, while also encouraging co-location of materials within one coherent community (i.e., science educators).
- In the humanities, **Knowledge Commons** (previously Humanities Commons) offers “knowledge creators” the ability to create their own spaces, manage content, and benefit from a shared repository.
- **COVE** or Collaborative Organization for Virtual Education, offers a platform for peer-reviewed, open-access content, including teaching materials.²⁷
- The **Zooniverse** project builder, is a direct outgrowth of the citizen-science platform Galaxy Zoo and permits people from all fields to create their own citizen-science projects.²⁸

In the publishing world, the model of each publishing house functioning as its own kingdom is quickly fading. A handful of innovative presses have put in place technical solutions for publishing what would be considered “custom” projects on a common infrastructure.

- **Manifold.** The open source platform for innovative publishing, offers support for both self-hosting or a hosted option.²⁹
- **Fulcrum**, the publishing platform run by University of Michigan Press and Library, offers publishers a way to publish enhanced ebooks in branded collections.

Platforms offering access to compute capacity and tools:

- **Open OnDemand** is an open source web portal run by researchers at the Ohio Supercomputer Center to provide access to high-performance computing.
- **Galaxy**,³⁰ a “free, open source system for analyzing data, authoring workflows, training and education, publishing tools, [and] managing infrastructure,” boasts a community of over 500,000 users worldwide and thousands of tools.

The notion of sharing proven infrastructure as a service for others applies to primary source materials as well. Services that have solved the problem for themselves offer solutions (for a fee) to others.

For example, the subscription-based scholarly content platform JSTOR began offering “infrastructure services” in 2023 to libraries and other content holders.³¹

Has the emergence of reliable platform solutions meant that fewer project leaders choose to build an entire project or platform alone? Not necessarily. Some project leads want total control over the form of the gateway so still opt to build; for others without a steady stream of funding, the perceived cost of using an existing platform or maintenance fees may be a factor. Finally, even though many platforms and tools are built using open source code, there can still be obstacles to finding and making the best use of these existing elements.

Approach: Convergence and “coopetition”

Funders at federal agencies and private foundations have long sought ways to encourage collaboration among PIs. Tactics range from hosting workshops to encouraging them to independently identify potential partners, to offering funding calls that require teams to submit with partners, to issuing more direct guidance.

In the report *Funding for Sustainability*, some funders noted that they had encouraged certain teams to work together. “Sometimes, you have so many entrants in a space—or a set of tangential spaces—that no one can succeed. Part of the solution is consolidation.” This funder has discreetly asked some of the organisation’s funding recipients to collaborate, “much to (their) chagrin.”³²

A recent example of a strategic approach to this situation is the National Institutes of Health’s “coopetition” model. This approach, defined by Program Director Ishwar Chandramouliswaran, merges the notions of cooperation and competition to actively encourage projects to find ways to work together. Observing the proliferation of generalist repositories, Chandramouliswaran developed the Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative or GREI program, which consists of seven repositories, Dataverse, Dryad, Figshare, Mendeley Data, Open Science Framework, Vivli, and Zenodo. Each of the repositories has adopted the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles to better share and reuse NIH-funded data. The aim is to develop interoperable repositories that cooperate on common standards, support data sharing and enable discoverability across repositories while still allowing for unique project features like custom visualizations, tools and metadata. Working groups focus on use cases, metadata and search, metrics and community engagement. A parallel effort, the US Repository Network (supported by SPARC and run by the Confederation of Open Access Repositories) has a goal of “breaking down institutional silos and developing a more cohesive approach and greater collaboration.”³³

These efforts are relatively new, but they show that funders recognize the importance of facilitating collaboration, sharing, and re-use among PIs and illustrate important steps towards modeling a culture of collaboration and re-use at the project level.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND QUESTIONS FOR DISCUSSION

- **Develop a taxonomy of “science gateways”** to define and quantify existing gateways, according to domain, function, and structure. This framework, which could also produce an inventory, could help identify more operational commonalities and needs among what otherwise can appear to be a sea of one-off projects.
- **Design a platform of platforms** to permit co-location of related gateways, at a price researchers in all fields can afford. Current offerings of shared platforms often target STEM grantees who can afford substantial annual fees, or very simple content sharing platforms for scholars to share written work. Could there be a solution between those extremes, to permit more PIs to host/co-locate gateways? How large is the market of potential gateway providers that would benefit from this solution? How great might the benefits be for co-locating gateways in adjacent fields?
- **Evaluate the effectiveness of methods for driving collaboration.** Do funder mandates lead to more efficient, valuable gateways? How, otherwise, do project leads choose to undertake collaborations?
- **Construct a new logic for collaboration.** If funder encouragement does not work, what will incentivize reuse, when the current system neither rewards the creators of the original solution, nor those planning to use or extend it? What new system of incentives, or even funding structures, would actively promote re-use?
- **To what extent could AI be leveraged** to more quickly identify “best fit,” open source code from relevant gateways, to increase awareness of potential re-use opportunities?

Challenge: Institutional support

Decades into the era of investment in digital creation, despite massive leaps in innovative tools for discovery, gateway builders and users are still having trouble knowing where to go when they need help. This challenge still exists both in the virtual sphere and in the physical geography of a university campus.

College and university campuses have a wealth of technical support and expertise available, but these often exist across a variety of departments or units within a single campus, often including the library, IT, academic computing, or academic departments. Studies done a decade ago mapped out this situation on several campuses in the US and UK, where everything including HPC, developer time, strategic guidance, and storage space might be available to faculty, but often was hosted at different units throughout one campus.³⁴

The situation today is not resolved. Anthony Caldwell, the Assistant Director of UCLA's Digital Research Consortium, reported that many on his campus complain that "no one knows where everything is and how to get help," leading him a few years ago to create a map of resources on campus. Joseph Yun, a gateway builder who has been active in the Gateways community, notes that "most gateway PIs don't realize there are many potential partners at their universities." Barr von Oehsen, director of the Pitt Supercomputer Center, noted that the landscape of technical guidance and support on his campus was in transition and siloed.

An exploratory study conducted in 2023 suggested one reason for this: Humanists might not immediately recognize the term "science gateway" as something relevant to them. Interviews with librarians and humanists suggested that they are often unaware of the range of support that is offered on campus.³⁵

Sometimes the resources are hiding in plain sight, and it is not just humanists who are not taking advantage of them. Coordination and cooperation among those different units is still very much a work in progress.

Approach: Emergence of campus-support hubs

The host institution is a key stakeholder in most—if not all—large-scale grants to researchers and builders of academic cyberinfrastructure, offering support to the project in the form of staff time, office space, or other forms of in-kind support. When digital assets are one of the project outputs, the university may offer to help support, sustain, or make those digital assets (dataset, software, digital humanities project, gateway, etc.) available post-grant.³⁶ In return, it may benefit from a generous overhead rate.

From the perspective of the funder, the reputation and reliability of the host institution and its willingness to vouch for the project team is a factor in determining whether to award the grant in the first place. Funder assessment of an institution's likelihood of honoring promises of support often played a large role in their willingness to fund researchers at those institutions.³⁷

Over the last two decades, universities and colleges have taken steps to help faculty and students building digital projects in a range of ways. The 2010s saw the rise of Digital Humanities Centers and Digital Scholarship Centers, often affiliated with the campus library.^{38,39} Some, like the Center for History and Media at George Mason University or MATRIX at Michigan State University, were focused mainly on building software, tools, and partnerships with scholars on large-scale digital research platforms. Others were conceived of as centers for sharing information and training faculty and students in the methodologies of digital scholarship and communications.⁴⁰ A recent example of support for advancing the teaching and information-sharing approach include the Digital Studies Institute at University of Michigan, described as a “center for research and dialogue.”⁴¹

Since 2020, a new movement has begun to take hold on some college campuses. Modeled after **Open Source Program Offices (OSPOs)** that exist in private technology companies, the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation began funding the creation of OSPOs on college campuses to provide information, training, guidance, and sometimes direct building or hosting support for project leaders.

According to a recent Sloan call for proposals, “We believe that better institutional support for open source practices can accelerate and sustain the development of software and other research outputs within universities through a number of mechanisms. Robust documentation and clear project governance can substantially lower barriers to the contribution to and maintenance of individual projects, and lower barriers for students, postdocs, and faculty to continue engaging with a project as they move from one institution to another.”⁴²

The OSPOs on different campuses each have slightly different goals and approaches, but the overall ethos of open source is to encourage collaboration and re-use. As Stephanie Lieggi, the Executive Director of the OSPO at UC Santa Cruz stated, “Open source has been looked at by universities for a while but ... this more networked approach... help[s] build upon what other people are doing.”

While not explicitly stated, this push to accelerate adoption of open source practices can be seen as part of an underlying sustainability strategy. Encouraging the use of open source code is, in a sense, a necessary if not sufficient step towards sustainability. By creating projects, platforms, gateways, and tools using open source code, they are more easily shareable, extendable, affordable, and re-usable by others, good conditions for encouraging sustainability. Some OSPOs recognize this and have taken on the role of coaching project leaders in the suite of skills needed beyond coding.

The OSPO at Johns Hopkins, for example, places emphasis on the importance of understanding user needs and the importance of incentivizing engagement. This suite of business strategy skills are a vital part of creating sustainable gateways. When deployed under the umbrella of an OSPO, this training would be relevant to any team leading an innovative digital initiative, whether open source or not.⁴³ In addition to efforts focused on guidance and training, a new grant addressing the need for further professionalization and capacity for building complex projects launched in 2022. Schmitt Futures’ Virtual Institute of Scientific Software (VISS) grants provide institutions with “access to full-time professional engineers and state of the art technology to develop high quality, maintainable and adaptable software.”⁴⁴

Models for campus-level coordination. One recent example of bringing the resources of a campus together in one physical space is the Research Alliance at Montana State University. Launched by the University Library in 2023, the Alliance brings together expertise in planning and proposal development, project implementation and leadership, publication and preservation, and measuring impact and engagement. Dean of the Library Doralyn Rossmann had noticed that people were “spending lots of time looking for help” and hopes this new arrangement enhances visibility of available services and helps make it easier to find collaborators across disciplines.⁴⁵

FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND QUESTIONS FOR DISCUSSION

- **Facilitate campus-level discussions across disciplinary lines** to address the range of supports available for digital initiatives—tech transfer, OSPO, DH Center, Library—and methods for best offering these supports to gateway builders.
- **Evaluate the function of the different types of supporting units on campuses**—OSPOs, DH Centers, digital scholarship units and others—to assess if, how, and to what extent professional- and business-supported strategies are helping to create more impactful, scalable and sustainable gateways.
- **Revisit approaches to creating directories** of gateways, of projects, of RSEs, and of their portfolios of work. Could there be a way to leverage and share valuable information not just about gateways and the tools, code, and content they hold, but also the developers and engineers who design and maintain them?

Challenge: Defining and delivering a strong value proposition

Please, oh please, do not “build it” and hope “they” will come! This fallacy—that building something great is all that is needed to draw an enthusiastic audience of users—has been spotlighted time and again regarding digital resources in undergraduate education in the humanities and social sciences,⁴⁶ scholarly digital resources,⁴⁷ library special collections,⁴⁸ and science gateways in particular.^{49, 50}

Many gateway leaders express the desire to engage users, whether those who contribute content or data or those who use the data or tools the gateway provides. Creating a space for scholars and students to interact and to support community interactions “feels like one of the most complex ambitions that creators have,” according to Charles Watkinson, Associate University Librarian and Director of the University of Michigan Press, but “how to seed and then maintain community interaction to the level that the community becomes invested in and continually contributing to the project” remains a real challenge.

A “lessons-learned” report on the decade-long, NSF-funded Earthcube project as it wound down, noted that a key sustainability challenge was that “groups generally underestimated the time and difficulty of engaging the user community and supporting uptake through training and outreach.”⁵¹ This user-engagement challenge is similar to challenges documented for those creating open source scientific software, where the robustness of a contributor community can be vital to its long-term sustainability.⁵²

Challenges around building and engaging audiences may be due to a few factors. While project leaders may understand that audience needs should be of central importance, in practice pinpointing a strong “value proposition” and truly understanding what a community needs requires time and expertise and can be especially hard to accomplish with objectivity by project founders.

Assessing whether or not a project is actually addressing those needs is not simple either. Pls often struggle with the best way to define the impact of their gateway-related work. Throughout the interviews and workshops, participants made it clear they understand the importance of demonstrating the value and impact of their projects but lack clarity about how to define and measure impact and value. According to Stephanie Lieggi, “How to measure open source metrics in academia, including things like measuring social impact...and value within the university, is still a work in progress.”

How to improve the likelihood that science gateways and other innovative digital projects are addressing real and pressing community needs? How to express the impact of that work in a clear and compelling way? This section suggests several approaches to this challenge, including establishing processes that better identify community needs upstream, training project teams so they are able to shape and refine value propositions, and standardizing impact metrics.

Approach: Building by placing user needs first

There are some fields that have long-standing methods to let community needs inform investments in large-scale digital initiatives. In astronomy and astrophysics, a decadal survey (conducted on behalf of the NSF and deployed via the National Academies) addresses the current environment and future opportunities for investment in the field. The most recent report, *Pathways to Discovery in Astronomy and Astrophysics for the 2020s*, is a broad and deep agenda-setting document that also includes recommendations on the technology and instrumentation needed.⁵³

In the earth sciences, the NSF-funded Earthcube project and the community support organization ESIP⁵⁴ provide an example of intentionally bringing together scholars in a field to benefit from the shared intelligence of disciplinary needs. Earthcube, funded through NSF's Directorate for Geosciences (GEO) and the NSF Office of Advanced Cyberinfrastructure (OAC),⁵⁵ was intended to "nurture a well-connected ecosystem of interoperable data, tools, models, storage, and compute resources." While NSF funding for Earthcube ended after ten years (often the maximum life of a grant in this funding track), the community identified core elements of 60 funded projects and strategies to support them.⁵⁶

Community collaborations can be among peer universities. The COVID Information Commons was a partnership "between Columbia and several other institutions," according to Rob Cartolano, Associate Vice President for Digital Programs and Technology Services at Columbia University. "It's something that from the very start was done as a cross-institutional effort, recognizing that you know you're more likely to have partners at peer institutions than down the hallway."⁵⁷

Some "top-down," high-profile projects attempting to create grand solutions for national audiences have struggled, including the NSF's National Science Digital Library,⁵⁸ Mellon's Project Bamboo,⁵⁹ and the National Data Service.⁶⁰ Even the Digital Public Library of America, with an initial target of being America's library, has struggled to pinpoint a powerful value proposition; in 2024, having amassed over 52 million images, texts, videos, and sounds, and running a significant deficit, announced plans to seek a "sustainable, long-term home."⁶¹

If some of the “top-down” approaches to creating an ecosystem level of support struggle; there may be more hope when the solutions emerge from within a community of practice. For the field of archaeology, the **Archaeology Data Service** was originally created in 1996 by a consortium of departments of archaeology from several UK universities.⁶² The **Protein Data Bank**, founded in 1971 at Brookhaven National Laboratory, consists of an archive of “3D structure data for large biological molecules (proteins, DNA, and RNA) essential for research and education in fundamental biology, health, energy, and biotechnology.”⁶³ These disciplinary services have emerged from within their communities as needs arose.

Other projects with broad-sounding ambitions are taking aim at much more specific targets. The NSF-funded **National Data Platform**, led by a team at the San Diego Supercomputer Center, is very clear that their approach is user-driven. According to Ilkay Altintas, Chief Data Science Officer at SDSC, “everything we do needs to be built with the user in mind, and with what they are willing to pay, and how that paying happens... If you build it [just] because you think it is a good idea...it will not be enough.” Eighteen months into the project, the National Data Platform has begun by focusing on a workflow for a specific use case: “an educator trying to use a large data set or to run a data challenge.”

A deep understanding of user needs is vital, whether or not the project emerges organically from within a community. What steps can help support PIs in making sure they continue to focus on user needs and delivering value as the project progresses? We discuss that next.

Approach: Training and consulting

One approach to sharpening the value proposition of science gateways is to train project leaders to better understand the concept; they also need to learn the skills for conducting landscape analysis (“competitive assessment”) and qualitative exploration of users and stakeholders (“customer discovery”), the two pillars of a solid value proposition.

NSF’s I-Corps program, founded in 2011 by NSF,⁶⁴ offers \$50,000 in funding to teams so that they can undertake an intensive, 7-week, training program which requires them to undertake a minimum of 100 customer-discovery interviews. The methodology they use draws from the world of commercial start-ups, and admission has heavily favored commercially focused projects. Indeed, when reviewing the sustainability of eleven earth-sciences projects of Earthcube, authors urged NSF to invest in a “program similar to I-CORPS, but targeted at projects that aim to become (actually or effectively) not-for-profit organizations... [in order to] bridge the critical gap between project inception and the period when the initial leaders must first develop a formal governance mechanism.”⁶⁵

Other programs, including the Focus Week training by SGX3, do offer a foundational curriculum of business strategy training carefully tailored to academic research projects that—while intended to grow—have an expectation of remaining in the not-for-profit space.⁶⁶

Approach: Standardizing impact metrics

Value, once defined, can still be hard to measure. Participants in our Brain Trust exercise mentioned traditional academic metrics such as the number of publications or citations. Others focused on the number and variety of users and collaborators to a project. Some discussed seminars and tutorials offered and the number of students enrolled. Other responses included endorsements and winning prizes. But most noted that which metrics to choose were not always obvious, and often not a required element of early planning stages. A funder mentioned that even when people do measure usage it is often not shared, which does not help to build trust with their communities.

Community-based standards for how impact data is gathered and assessed are just beginning to emerge. The need to capture impact via agreed-upon measures is a first step; getting campus administrations to consider it for tenure and promotion is another. As Megan Forbes of the OSPO at Johns Hopkins noted, it may be necessary to use impact metrics to make the case “for recognition of the work because it doesn’t often count for tenure. This could include getting citations for work, agreeing on metrics, showing PIs how to get DOIs, and seeing how things are spreading. Impact metrics can lead to operational support.”

What to measure differs for each gateway, but some gateways are better than others at methodically gathering data. In the case of emerging fields, like community-based digital humanities, even when metrics are gathered, they may not be well aligned with the metrics that are most “valuable” for tenure and promotion.⁶⁷

Several projects have emerged that address this challenge. Examples include:

- **MakeDataCount.org:** Supported by the non-profit Datacite with advisory members from universities and non-profits throughout the U.S. and Europe, their aim is to develop community-led, meaningful, open-data metrics, defined as “contextualized quantitative or qualitative measures of how open datasets are accessed or utilized.”⁶⁸
- **CHAOS:** This Linux Foundation project, started in 2017, is focused on creating metrics, metrics models, and software to better understand open source community health on a global scale. In

addition to defining dozens of metrics, CHAOSS includes data analytics GrimoireLab, an open source kit for gathering and visualizing this data.^{69,70}

- **Open Ebooks** efforts, such as OAPEN's Books Analytics Service dashboard.⁷¹
- The **NSF-funded workshop** in 2023, which addressed "Exploring National Infrastructure for Public Access and Impact Reporting"⁷²

FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND QUESTIONS FOR DISCUSSION

- **Require training** for potential PIs on strategies for defining which metrics to measure.
- **Include more rigorous review of proposals** to evaluate plausibility of the stated value proposition and the willingness and ability of the project team to respond to user needs.
- Funders could **build in additional support for professional marketing and business strategy** from the early stages of a project, as this expertise is rarely found in the initial grant-funded team.
- How can funders and their grantees maintain the flexibility needed at the start of a new gateway, while also adopting a user-focused mindset to drive decision-making?

Challenge: Sustainable funding

When sustainability is on the agenda, a discussion about financial support is rarely far behind. A community survey of over 5,000 respondents conducted in 2014 found that gateway providers need to keep “in mind how they will finance their work over time.”⁷³ Funders, PIs, university administrators, and anyone who works with digital projects often identify securing financial support as a persistent challenge.

Studies that detail the ongoing costs of digital projects offer some insight into the challenges of understanding the operational costs of science gateways.⁷⁴ Defining the boundaries of the “gateway” itself is sometimes the first challenge, as many are deeply embedded within larger departments. The citizen-science project **eBird** is part of the Cornell Lab of Ornithology in the Center for Avian Population Studies and Macaulay Library.⁷⁵ The data platform **SciServer** benefits from its relationship to the larger Institute for Data-Intensive Engineering and Science (IDIES).⁷⁶

While the costs of data repositories, for example, have been studied in some detail,⁷⁷ PIs of different types of projects find it difficult to envisage what future, ongoing, post-grant costs will be. Tracy Brown, Manager of Web and Mobile Applications at the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC), notes that “PIs need to start [thinking about] sustainability from the start. They don’t plan past Year One... They think once the site is up, they are done. They do not realize that if they do not maintain it, it will come down.”

This issue often comes to a head when a project team is hoping to **transition from a grant-funded project to an ongoing service or product**. The original grant budget developed at proposal stage may not (and should not) look the same as the budget required for transforming the innovative project into a reliable, ongoing service. While some costly stages have been completed, many other activities will continue indefinitely (administration, maintenance, upgrades, security, outreach, and user research) or need to be added.

There are different ways to address the funding challenge. One approach is to have PIs focus on lowering the upfront and ongoing costs of supporting gateways through greater collaboration, less customization, and guarding against overengineering (as discussed above), as well as developing reliable sources of volunteer and in-kind support. That said, even the most efficiently run gateway will still have some costs to cover, and new approaches have emerged to address this.

Approach: Collaborative funding

Several interviewees mentioned “greater collaboration” as a path to a more sustainable digital ecosystem. Often collaboration in this sense refers to partnerships among gateways or PIs, but over the past decade, there has been much experimentation with *collaborative funding mechanisms*, new ways to pool funding to support the work of gateways that already exist.

Some examples include:

- **Invest in Open Infrastructure**, founded in 2018, is a not-for-profit organization whose work includes funding pilots to “offer unique opportunities to invest in innovative funding models for open infrastructure.”⁷⁸
- **Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS)** is a Canadian effort created in 2017 to provide a shared funding mechanism among “influential organisations committed to helping secure OA and OS infrastructure well into the future.”⁷⁹
- **Pooled funding models also emerged in the publishing sphere**, with projects like Knowledge Unlatched, which pooled contributions (“pledges”) from a certain number of libraries, needed to “flip” a collection of scholarly monographs to open access.⁸⁰

Funders have also made efforts to **incentivize collaborations across institutional and geographic boundaries**. For example, begun in 2009, the Belmont Forum is an international partnership focused on environmental research that brings together funding agencies from 28 countries. Their calls for proposals (Collaborative Research Actions) require applicants to include projects “co-developed by natural scientists, social scientists, and stakeholders that hail from at least three countries.”⁸¹

Similarly, launched in 2018, the D//F (**Digital Infrastructure Insights Fund**) is a multi-funder initiative by the Ford Foundation, Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, Omidyar Network, Schmidt Futures and Open Collective whose aim is to create a “body of research and implementation insights that advance our goal to ensure a public commons of technology, sustainably developed and maintained, for the benefit of everyone.”⁸²

Shifting the notion of who ought to be paying: In the scholarly publishing realm, the TOME (Toward an Open Monograph Ecosystem) pilot tested a model of university support for the publication of open-access scholarly monographs. While funding was not pooled, shifting responsibility for paying from readers to the university (or library) itself prompted some questions: What does it cost to create

and sustain digital work? and What people or organizations ought to be paying for it?⁸³ We might ask if there is a version of this that might apply to support for gateways.

As recent work of the Ford and Sloan Foundations asks: Should cyberinfrastructure be considered a common good that merits broad public support? Are there other examples we can consider that show new models of aligning sources of funding for core infrastructure?^{84, 85} Examples abound of academic gateways and tools that are launched—or acquired by— commercial vendors. Is this pathway from community-created to commercially-owned desirable for end users in the academic community, if the tools are freely available? If not, what academic-funded model can be designed to support development of tools, code, gateways, and virtual workspaces? Can we professionalize the gateway space, without commercializing it?

Approach: Funder “sustainability” tracks

Some funders have begun offering “sustainability” tracks to support gateways in transitioning from their original grant funding to their next phase. Within NSF’s Cyberinfrastructure for Sustained Scientific Innovation (CSSI) track, Transition to Sustainability is a one-time award intended for those who “would like to execute a well-defined sustainability plan for existing CI with demonstrated impact in one or more areas of science and engineering supported by NSF.”⁸⁶

In 2022, NSF’s Directorate for Technology, Innovation and Partnerships launched the POSE program, Pathways to Enable Open-Source Ecosystems, with the aim of offering funds to help transition already-existing open source products into “sustainable high-impact open source ecosystems.”⁸⁷ Other programs within NSF as well as other funders, both public and private, offer funding for business strategy, often as part of larger proposals to extend work already underway that has some evidence of community support.

This funding can offer a vital buffer, as one experienced PI noted that while “commercially, the ongoing budget for getting out to market is larger than the development budget... [It is] somewhat odd that the level of [sustainability] funding available [from funders is often] less than the construction budget.”

When these approaches fail, gateway leaders need to make choices: sunsetting or keeping what is valuable. More research and guidance is needed for identifying when this decision point should take place.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND QUESTIONS FOR DISCUSSION

- **Assess the extent to which collaborative funding models have succeeded.** What criteria have been most successful in identifying which projects to support? How good are these funding groups at choosing projects that subsequently thrive?
- **Research the “sustainability” tracks from major funders.** Closer examination would reveal assumptions about what it takes to transition from a grant-funded to an independent service. Some appear to offer very modest funding, suggesting sustainability is envisioned as a low-effort end state; others offer more, anticipating the need to hire and build up an organization.
- **Design more viable “off ramps” when no further funding is available.** Perhaps “sunsetting” is the most pressing motivator for collaboration. More work is needed to develop routine paths to maintaining the valuable elements when a gateway closes.

Challenge: Leadership, staffing, governance

At the heart of the success of any science gateway, digital initiative or other online resource of any type are the people who created it and continue to run it. As one funder noted, funding decisions, “more than before, [are] about the people.”

Teams of gateways creators, digital humanities leaders, or other innovative academic software project groups are often a mix of disciplinary specialists, programmers, designers, data managers, and project managers. For grant-funded projects, the terms of a proposal may define to some degree the way they will work together and the roles they will play; for projects emanating from larger organizations, there may be a project charter or other understanding of how the team will come together around this digital “start-up” project. Should the project continue to grow, it may reach a point where it is possible to have full-time, dedicated management and staff; but this is still the exception to the rule. And here is where some persistent problems appear.

Leadership. In 2008, *Sustainability and Revenue Models for Online Academic Resources*⁸⁸ highlighted the importance of having an “entrepreneurial” mindset as a key factor in predicting the likelihood of a project’s sustainability. Would the project leader be able to make hard decisions, address shortcomings, assess with clarity the competitive landscape, and take advantage of opportunities as they arose? In short, could academic scholars, after receiving grants to build gateways, portals, digital collections, and so forth, transform from an experimental, research-focused, grant-based mindset to a goal-focused, entrepreneurial one?

Today, funders still place significant importance in choosing grantees they see as possessing a strong entrepreneurial sensibility as a key factor in determining the likelihood that a project will flourish. As PI Joseph Yun noted, the focus in grantmaking should not be “on the viability of the research, but rather on the viability of the leadership to make the research work and grow into something that will sustain into the future; this is much more aligned with how venture capital works.”

Time allocation and focus. Even the most energetic and entrepreneurial leader needs time to accomplish goals, but we still see PIs and teams only able to devote fractions of time, juggling project oversight with their own research programs, teaching, and other grant-funded work. This can make it difficult for a project to make speedy progress; it can also remove some live-or-die urgency from decision making and execution.

Succession planning. A related issue, still often unresolved, concerns succession planning. According to Zentner, an experienced entrepreneur, there are real risks involved for science gateways run by a solo PI. “When the PI retires, who is going to take that on?” he asks. “There is a significant risk in running a gateway platform where there is only one person on staff who understands it anymore... When [the PI] retires, will the host institution invest in training new staff how to support it?”

Maintaining and nurturing a strong pipeline of developer talent. The skills, entrepreneurial drive, and longevity of project leaders is one challenge; but there are many more people involved in building or maintaining a science gateway or other innovative digital initiative. Just about a decade ago, their roles were vital but not always fully valued and often misunderstood. In 2010, Neil Chue Hong and his colleagues at the University of Edinburgh founded the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) with the notion that “helping individuals and institutions understand the vital role that software plays in research would accelerate progress in every field of scientific and academic endeavour.”⁸⁹

Approach: Professionalization and the rise of the RSE

Has the environment for labor vastly changed? Maybe not yet. “Broadly speaking, there is widespread recognition that there is too much unpaid labor that is not being supported and that the burnout problem is very severe,” according to Sayeed Choudhury, Associate Dean for Digital Infrastructure and Director of the Open Source Programs Office (OSPO) at Carnegie Mellon University. “Within a university context it may not be unpaid labor, but it’s probably student labor; graduate students didn’t come to grad school to become software maintainers. They came for other reasons, so we may not have an unpaid labor issue, but we certainly have a misalignment of why people came and what they’re doing and whether that’s sustainable or not.”

In one of the truly innovative marks of progress over the last decade, the UK-based Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) has essentially created and effectively advocated for the notion of “research software engineering” as a job title and a viable career path within academia.⁹⁰ Their work in this space since 2012 has gone a long way toward defining and advocating for the role of the Research Software Engineer.^{91, 92}

Approach: Culture of support

While many of the challenges and solutions in this report address practical tactics or strategies to employ, some of the most creative thinking we heard throughout the study concerned not what you do, but how you do it.

The underlying challenges Julia Stewart Lowndes observed are indeed troubling: people don't have an intentional positive framework for their work, and the default leads to overwork, burnout, a sense of isolation, lack of confidence and trust within teams, skill mismatches, or knowledge loss due to staff turnover. Lowndes, founder and director of **Openscapes**, noted that these feelings do not just make individuals feel bad; they lead to workplace behaviors that effectively slow down time to science. And the bad feelings—and behaviors that lead to them—are repeated from team to team mainly because people don't know of any other way to work.

Her organization has taken a novel approach to reengineer how people work and work with each other, dealing in ideas not commonly discussed in technical or business strategy settings, like “kindness.” Openscapes considers kindness critical to open science and works with teams to establish open processes that are clear and transparent, and premised on clear documentation and sharing, grounded in the idea that building something to last requires many little things reinforced over time.

This is not just a friendly approach; it has real implications for innovation and sustainability as well, by creating a culture of trust and psychological safety which leads to faster research and greater access. As Julia Stewart Lowndes noted, “we can't solve [major global problems] if you can't talk to your team or get reimbursed without 20 emails back and forth.”

An example of how the Openscapes approach can work is the earthaccess Python library that permits users to access and search NASA's earth science data. By applying Openscapes processes and principles, it went from being a resource used by a few dozen people and requiring 30 lines of code to a resource used by tens of thousands of people and maintained by NASA staff across data centers as well as by the open-source community.

This focus on strengthening teams is echoed in the work of Jessica Hammer at the Center for Transformational Play, who has noted that focusing too much on success can lead to a reluctance to try things that fail and focusing on the safe choice rather than the revolutionary one. It can also create an environment within teams where people are reluctant to say that they are uncertain or say that they need to learn something. They pull on a “mask” of perfection.

Work environments are not solely determined by the internal dynamic of the group but also by larger, systemic forces associated with inequality. Establishing work environments that encourage a sense of belonging was an important finding of the American Council of Learned Societies' *Commission on*

Fostering and Sustaining Digital Scholarship. Aimed at studying “questions of ...access in the creation of and access to digital resources and projects related to social and racial justice,”⁹³ the group’s discussions underlined the importance of meeting teams where they are. In the UK, similar efforts have been underway to analyze and address systemic inequality among leaders of large-scale grants, the type that are typically needed to support building a science gateway.^{94,95}

Approach: Governance models: Rise of consortia

The origins and aspirations of a project can inform the shape it takes, its governance and ultimately its likelihood of finding a sustainable path. The “lone PI” or small team can face challenges of scale, particularly in the humanities and social sciences, where grant funding is scarce. Larger initiatives, including partnerships and projects aspiring to be “national” in scale, do not necessarily have an easier time of it.

In recent years, consortia have emerged as a way to support new gateway-like projects. These organizations have become more widespread, attracting the interest of scholars to better understand what forms best support sustainable growth. Members of the Stakeholder Alignment Collaborative argue for what they call a “minimum viable consortia”: a governance structure that remains sufficiently agile so as to avoid institutional inertia, while permitting shifts in focus as stakeholder needs shift. Aligning with stakeholder needs, and “adjusting” as those needs adjust, is a key element of this model.⁹⁶

FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND QUESTIONS FOR DISCUSSION

- **Research the impact and measurable change seen as a result of implementing open processes, but also from implementing “culture change” that prioritizes collaboration, teamwork, and open principles.**
- **Focus—from funders and from teams—on funding to support staffing from fields not always included in early grant stages, such as business strategy and marketing/outreach.**
- **What operational elements of gateway creation, governance, and ongoing management could be handled by a supporting organization?**

Recommendations and Food for Thought

This report highlights examples of concrete steps that appear to be bearing fruit; all merit attention. We would like to see the ideas here serve as the basis for further discussion, research, and action by those in discrete disciplinary communities, at higher education institutions, and within funding bodies.

MORE COLLABORATION

The theme of collaboration and the need for more of it came across loud and clear through focus groups and interviews, whether what was needed was more discussions among PIs, among funders, or among university administrators. Funders, particularly working in concert, are in a unique position to encourage collaboration, so that project leaders seek out others working in adjacent areas, using relevant tools and infrastructure, and sharing skills and expertise.

Short of an altruistic decision to cooperate, what solutions can be encouraged to avoid the duplication of effort so many practitioners report seeing? If national-scale funding efforts like the Wellcome Trust's funding of PubMed Central are not possible in the United States, are there still methods to incentivize users to collaborate across institutions to build best-in-class solutions that support the scholarly mission and can remain academic-owned?

FINDING COMMUNITY WHERE IT ALREADY IS

While we see steps being taken to encourage gateway leads to “engage community” and address audience needs, can more be done to go where the communities already are? Could there be a greater role for scholarly societies to play in funding, building, and supporting cyberinfrastructure, gateways, or other innovative digital initiatives that are needed, and—most important—identifying how they

will be supported over the long term? In the humanities, the Modern Language Association (MLA) has started to do this, with the creation of the shared workspace Knowledge Commons (formerly Humanities Commons).

But for the most part, scholarly societies themselves seem more focused on their traditional roles of journal publication and annual meeting conveners. This is understandable, but as scholarly work has begun more and more to inhabit digital platforms and virtual workspaces, the organizations that already represent “the community” seem extremely well positioned to play a guiding role in major investments for designing these spaces. What obstacles keep this from happening?

DEFINING THE ROLE OF PUBLIC SUPPORT (WHO “SHOULD” BE PAYING?)

It is not getting cheaper to build and maintain gateways. Mandates and the desire to make the fruits of taxpayer-funded research and software openly available tend to exclude some categories of financial support (eg. paid access), without suggesting how to replace it.

As Michael Zentner pointed out, funders who balk at offering ongoing support for gateways, instead employing funds to support new, innovative work, are missing a key point. “If gateways do enable advancement of science,” according to Zentner, “then [funders] are actually investing in new science by investing in the sustainability of the digital platforms.”

Funders including Ford and Sloan have begun this conversation, but could this discussion take place on a wider scale, involving all stakeholders in scholarly research—to analyze and define, and decide which elements of the scholarly communications fabric ought to be publicly supported, and how? Could a vision of the benefits of transformative, free, open scholarly spaces somehow stitch together the current fragmentation of the funding landscape?

EXPANDING AND RATIONALIZING CAMPUS-LEVEL STRATEGY

Campus-level support seems to expand and contract over time. The 2010s saw the rise of digital humanities centers, digital scholarship offices and the rise of the research software engineer. Today, OSPOs begin to dot the academic landscape. Rather than creating more new spaces, **how can a campus strategy see beyond unnecessarily narrow containers** of “science gateway,” “digital humanities,” or even “open source” and acknowledge the common challenges that all innovative digital initiatives are facing:

- defining the core value of the project (or gateway or platform or software or service) based on deeply nuanced understanding of its present and potential users
- determining how to build it in a way that is not so precious and customized that it becomes difficult to maintain
- exploring a variety of sources of financial and non-financial support, including revenue generation, in ways that do not conflict with open-access mandates and mission.
- confronting a realistic timeline for determining if a project has reached its aims, or should be sunsetted (with all precautions taken to preserve original data, content, and documentation)

Digital initiatives have quickly evolved from being quirky projects alongside scholarship to being the main format for most stages of the scholarly workflow—including digital collections and archives, shared virtual labs and gateways, data repositories and publishing platforms—and enabling sharing, access, and preservation. The differences pale alongside the common challenges their leaders face when building and supporting them.

All that said, perhaps we are focused on fixing a model that is itself on the cusp of a seismic shift. According to Vipin Chaudhary, Department Chair, Computer and Data Sciences Department at Case Western University, the massive changes that Artificial Intelligence (AI) is bringing may be so revolutionary as to obviate the need for the gateways and other user interfaces we have just spent a few decades designing and worrying about. Rather than concerning ourselves with building new edifices we then need to maintain, is there a more dynamic model coming that might require very little permanent structure?

Over the last decade and a half, the discussion of “sustainability” has bubbled to the surface in many disciplines, concerning many types of gateways: science gateways, digital initiatives, digitized collections at libraries, digital humanities, datasets and data repositories in the sciences, and software and code itself.

There are worthy models to explore to address sustainability challenges. Yet there still is not sufficient discussion taking place among members of different disciplinary communities, or across disciplinary or professional lines. Those working on sustainability—for any innovative scholarly digital initiative—have much more in common than they may realize.

This is a critical moment, if ever there was one. A population perhaps too enamored with AI before structures are in place to manage it; a federal government distrustful of science and the academy and eager to hide rather than share information; scholars and teachers uncertain of the future of their work and livelihoods. Science gateways are intended to share information widely and encourage further learning and discovery. Developing strategies to let this happen well, and widely, without waste, at a cost that is manageable, should be the goal for all associated with gateways.

For now, let us learn from examples we see around us and keep experimenting with new and better ways to use technology to provide wide access to the students, scholars, and learners of the world.

Endnotes

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Appendices

Appendix A: List of Participants

Ikay Altinas, *Chief Data Science Officer, San Diego Supercomputer Center*

Brett Bobley, *Director and Chief Information Officer, National Endowment for the Humanities*

Tracy Brown, *Manager, Web and Mobile Applications, Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC)*

Anthony Caldwell, *Assistant Director UCLA Digital Research Consortium Manager, University of California, Los Angeles*

Rob Cartolano, *Associate Vice President for Digital Programs and Technology Services, Columbia University*

Ishwar Chandramouliswaran, *Lead, FAIR Data & Resources, National Institutes of Health*

Vipin Chaudhary, *Department Chair, Computer and Data Sciences Department, Kevin J. Kranzusch Professor, Case Western University*

Sayeed Choudhury, *Associate Dean for Digital Infrastructure and Director of the Open Source Programs Office (OSPO), Carnegie Mellon University*

Jason Clark, *Head of ROADS, MSU Library, MSU Research Alliance*

Perry Collins, *Senior Program Officer, NEH Office of Digital Humanities*

Maytal Dahan, *Director of Advanced Computing Interfaces, Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC)*

Corine Farewell, *Director of UVM Innovations, University of Vermont*

Katrina Fenlon, *Assistant Professor, Associated with the Center for Archival Futures (CAFe), University of Maryland*

Megan Forbes, *Program Manager, Open Source Programs Office, Johns Hopkins University*

Josh Greenberg, *Program Director, Alfred P. Sloan Foundation*

Jessica Hammer, *Director, Center for Transformational Play, Carnegie Mellon University*

Martin Halbert, *NSF Coordinator, University Libraries, University of North Carolina, Greensboro*

Neil Chue Hong, *PI and founding Director, Software Sustainability Institute*

Patricia Hswe, *Program Director for Public Knowledge, Mellon Foundation*

Salwa Ismail, *Associate University Librarian for Digital Initiatives and Information Technology, University of California, Berkeley*

Daniel S. Katz, *Chief Scientist at the National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA), Research Associate Professor in the Siebel School of Computing and Data Science, and Research Associate Professor in the School of Information Sciences (iSchool), University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign*

Kerk Kee, *Virginia and Choc Hutcheson Professor in Mass Communication, Texas Tech University*

Christine Kirkpatrick, *Division Director, Research Data Services at San Diego Supercomputer Center*

Stephanie Lieggi, *Executive Director of OSPO, Executive Director of CROSS, University of California, Santa Cruz*

Julia Stewart Lowndes, *Director, OpenScapes*

Owen Monroe, *Intern, NEH Office of Digital Humanities*

Marlon Pierce, *Program Director, Directorate for Computer and Information Science and Engineering (CISE), Office of Advanced Cyberinfrastructure (OAC)*

Doralynn Rossman, *Dean of the Library, MSU Research Alliance*

Annalie Rugg, *Chief Information Officer at UCLA Center for Digital Humanities, University of California, Los Angeles*

Judy Ruttenberg, *Senior Director, Scholarship, Policy, and Engagement Strategy, Association of Research Libraries*

Joe Stubbs, *Manager, Cloud & Interactive Computing (CIC), Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC)*

Barr von Oehsen, *Vice Chancellor for Research Computing, Director, Pittsburgh Supercomputing Center, University of Pittsburgh*

Charles Watkinson, *Associate University Librarian for Publishing / Director, University of Michigan Press, University of Michigan*

Joseph Yun, *Artificial Intelligence and Innovation Architect and Research Professor of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Pitt IT and the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Pittsburgh Swanson School of Engineering*

Mike Zentner, *Director of Sustainable Scientific Software, University of California, San Diego*

Appendix B: Invitation to Participate

SUSTAINABILITY BLUEPRINT FACTORY - FOCUS GROUP INVITATION

Science Gateways are “web-based platform(s) that allow large audiences of researchers, educators, students, and the public to access complex, expensive resources such as supercomputers, scientific instruments, and large data sets.” Their sustainability challenges - similar to many innovative digital initiatives in higher education - are well documented: A lack of funds to support ongoing operations; difficulty maintaining the level of staffing and focus needed; project leads who do not demonstrate an entrepreneurial mindset; funders who prefer innovation to operations; and the natural growing pains of transitioning what may have begun as a research project to an ongoing, reliable service. These obstacles are not new or unknown. Yet despite copious documentation and many efforts over the last decade made to address these challenges, they persist.

The Sustainability Blueprint Factory is hosting a series of Focus Groups, each targeting a different approach to solving a “sustainability” issue, so that we may learn more about how these approaches are faring, what some practical tools or forms of support might be, and what experts in the field see as the most promising innovations taking place now. The Sustainability Blueprint Factory is one of several “Blueprint Factories,” incubators for new ideas and practical approaches that are part of the NSF-funded SGX3, A Center of Excellence to Extend Access, Expand the Community and Exemplify Good Practices.

OUR APPROACH

Focus Groups will be held starting in June 2024, and a summary of the sessions will be shared publicly in the Fall. Each Focus Group will consist of 6-8 individuals, selected for their expertise and engagement in a specific approach to sustaining innovative digital initiatives. Among the perspectives and topics already defined are:

The “host institution” perspective.

With a focus on the current emphasis on “open source program offices” this focus group will bring together campus- level administrators and practitioners in a range of units on campus, from the OSPO, to DH center to the office of Sponsored Research, to discuss how campuses are addressing the sustainability issues of digital initiatives & science gateways created and supported by their faculty and staff.

The Open Source Project Office (OSPO) has emerged on many campuses as a way to educate and encourage faculty and students to use Open Source code when building Gateways and other digital projects. This is seen as a core building block; necessary if not sufficient condition, to serve as the foundation for projects that are intended to grow within a community. By expanding the support for faculty, staff, and students to understand the benefits of OSS, OSPOs help the community build tools that are more likely to be extendable, re-usable, and free to use. This session will encourage participants to share examples of successes, and metrics they are using to measure impact of this approach.

The “consortial” approach.

Consortiums are starting to form with a vision and mission focused on supporting area(s) of research locally, regionally, and nationally where simplifying access to resources and services through gateways is part of the solution, e.g., the Ecosystem for ResearchNetworking (ERN). These consortiums are often motivated by democratizing access to these resources and services that preserves the openness within the research and education community yet provides the security necessary within today’s world. To get buy-in from the research and education community, many consortiums are forming working groups focused on finding solutions: they seek constant feedback from the community, use an iterative process design solutions useful to a majority of users, hold workshops and All Hands Meetings where the community comes together to share ideas and knowledge, run hands-on training, and leverage expertise within the consortium through distributed responsibilities.

How are consortiums starting to change the way we approach gateways? Is this supra-institutional model a more efficient path to designing large-scale Gateways? What funding models will emerge to support discovery and development at this scale?

Sustainability through shifting mindsets and practices

Funding models and improved cyberinfrastructure may go some distance in supporting the long-term viability of Science Gateways, but at the heart of any successful Science Gateway is a person or team of highly motivated, entrepreneurial, and collaborative leaders. For some fortunate people, these traits may come naturally, but not for all. Several innovative approaches have emerged over the last decade that look at sustainability in terms of a set of approaches or behaviors that are likely to have an

impact on how well a project is built; how likely it is to be sustained. This session brings together representatives of different “approaches” to compare approaches to behavior and mindset and its impact on sustainable outcomes. Openscapes, The Center for Transformational Play, and NSF’s entrepreneurial program iCorps, all have as a premise that it is not just what we do, but how we do it that matters.

The aim of the Focus Groups is to gather members of the academic community who are directly involved in some key aspect of creating, supporting or otherwise engaging with Science Gateways (or gateways in any scholarly field) to share their current thinking on the question how valuable digital resources can best be supported.

Appendix C: Focus Group Guide

DISCUSSION GUIDE FOR CAMPUS-BASED SOLUTIONS

Participants:

- OPSO leads, VP Tech, univ library, DH center, HPC Center

Introductions

- Name, role/affiliation.
- How YOU define a “sustainable” project.
- Experience with Sustainability issues relating to “Science Gateways” in particular?

Background, context

- What are persistent sustainability challenges
 - ◊ For the PIs you work with?
 - ◊ For college/univ administrators?
- What have you seen as the major advances in the last decade?

Campus-Level strategy?

- Today, how important is this topic to campus administrators? (what roles?)
- How do senior administrators assess the “value” of supporting gateways?
 - ◊ Is sustaining Gateways seen as **critical to the mission of the institution**?
- Does your unit **measure (or help to measure) “value”** of Gateways?

New Directions...

We see some new directions emerging; or that the landscape itself has changed! Let’s talk now about some specific “innovations” at the campus level.

- OSPOs
- Research Engineering. More centrally focused?
- Library’s support for education, creation, hosting?
- Degree of alignment with campus mission and priorities?
- DH centers?

Best Future

- What would the best outcome be - the role of campus in getting there?
- Areas where you see potential for improvement

- Areas where you see innovating approaches (aside from those already discussed).
- Current promising research in this space?

Suggestions for Practical tools, further research needs?

DISCUSSION GUIDE FOR “PROCESSES & APPROACHES”

Participants:

- OpenScapes
- Center for Transformational Play
- (Maybe NSF’s iCorps)

Background, context

- Experience with Sustainability issues relating to Science Gateways
- What have you seen as the major improvements in the ways things work now?
- What are persistent sustainability challenges?

Your theory of “change” and how it impacts sustainability?

New Directions...

We see some new directions emerging; or that the landscape itself has changed! What new innovations have you noticed (your own, or others’?)

- Describe some of the concerns or fears that people have as they come to your communities for the first time
- Tell us about tactics that help them overcome those concerns
- Tactics for encouraging funders to move away from proprietary research or are there divergent groups?

Best Future

What would the best outcome of your work be (vis a vis creating sustainable software, projects, etc..)

Areas where you see potential for improvement?

Areas where you see innovating approaches (aside from those already discussed)?

Appendix D: Brain Trust Method

Braintrust timings	
5 minutes	Facilitator Poses the Question (1 min) Group asks/answers questions (4 mins)
5 minutes	Rapid-fire Writing!
10 minutes	In teams of 2 or 3, consolidate and categorize.
20 minutes	Teams post and share thinking
	FULL GROUP DEBRIEF

Posing the question (5 mins)

(1 min) The facilitator poses the question - can read the script - and preps the group to think creatively.
(4 mins) The group can ask questions, raise issues.

Rapid fire writing! (5 mins)

Using Post-its, write down as many ideas as possible.

One idea per Post-it

Do not pause to refine!

Do not eliminate any ideas!

Consolidate in teams (10 mins)

Participants quickly select groups of 2-3 and set about consolidating their thoughts, removing duplicate ideas, and determining which category they want to place them in.

Sorting it Out (20 mins)

Participants place all Post-its on a pre-designed grid, according to where THEY think each belongs.

The choices are:

- Easy, just do it
- Highest impact
- Wild and crazy
- Important but requires investment

Each team appoints one member to place their Post-Its in the categories, briefly explaining their reasoning as they go.

Acknowledgements

This Blueprint Factory report offers a broad sampling of approaches, ideas, and persistent challenges facing gateways funders, builders, and practitioners today. The tableau presented here would not be nearly as rich as it is without the insight of the many experts whose experiences are reflected within it.

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